

MEDICAL LABS HAVE BEEN COMMITTED TO ENHANCING AND PRESERVING ANALYTICAL QUALITY AND THEY WILL KEEP DOING SO BY UTILIZING THE CURRENT INSTRUMENTS FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE.

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ABSTRACT

The cost of medical laboratory testing is commonly touted as the test's worth, but the tests' clinical advantages are just as crucial. Laboratory testing has an impact on clinical outcome and is generally acknowledged to be involved in clinical decision-making. Consequently, the importance of laboratory testing should be assessed against how it promotes good behaviors and results..

Introduction. The cost of medical laboratory testing is commonly touted as the test's worth, but the tests' clinical advantages are just as crucial. Laboratory testing has an impact on clinical outcome and is generally acknowledged to be involved in clinical decision-making. Consequently, the importance of laboratory testing should be assessed against how it promotes good behaviors and results. This includes the reporting phase, which guides clinical decisions and actions, as well as the testing phase, which entails choosing tests that could influence clinical decision-making [1,2]. The utility of medical laboratory tests can be increased if clinical decision support software and systems are concentrated on assisting clinical decisions addressing patient outcomes that are backed by evidence or consensus. To enhance laboratory services and ensure that they. Overall, the results support the deployment of cutting-edge technology and improved laboratory infrastructures to improve health outcomes worldwide. This evaluation highlights the importance of stakeholders working together to improve laboratory services and ensure that they are available, effective, and able to satisfy the changing needs of healthcare systems [3,4,5].

Material and methods. The clinical value of testing also depends on selecting a test that will improve clinical outcomes and interpreting the results so that the reports support beneficial clinical actions. An advising service that comprehends and communicates with doctors regarding test selection and interpretation must be in place. The clinical communications of the medical laboratory, which include in-person meetings, phone consultations, newsletters, and report interpretation comments, must thus be developed and expanded by laboratory personnel. Ideally, choosing clinically acceptable tests necessitates

understanding the clinical goal as well as the advantages and disadvantages of the various tests.

Results. Therefore, clinical recommendations for appropriate test utilization should be continuously updated by both physicians and laboratory experts. Both doctors and laboratory workers should be included in clinical decision support for test selection, and they should engage together on initiatives to better test selection. Another example of how laboratories might influence clinical outcomes by increasing collaboration on these themes is by making sure that test data are available in a timely manner relevant to the urgency of clinical decision making. Instead of reporting the outcomes of analysis, laboratory reports should concentrate on facilitating useful therapeutic measures. Reports should highlight the major findings, their clinical significance, and any potential beneficial treatment steps that might be indicated rather than sifting through the minutiae of study. Reports should be structured with an emphasis on interpretation and action, particularly for clinical tasks that the laboratory may help with, such as reflex testing or additional testing on the present sample.

Conclusions. This study looked at the quantity and trend of QI and QC papers in clinical laboratory practice. Our research suggests that the significant rise in the trend of QI and QC after 2000 may have been caused by the introduction of laboratory QI standards and the accreditation of clinical laboratory facilities. Our research demonstrates how vital it is to adhere to good clinical laboratory practice guidelines and how working together, certified and non-accredited enterprises may strengthen the quality management system and support consistent growth in the clinical laboratory industry

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